

Linear Chromodynamics Models for Hyperspectral Target Detection¹

A. Schaum
Naval Research Laboratory
Washington D.C.
schaum@nrl.navy.mil
202 767-9366

A. Stocker
Space Computer Corporation
Los Angeles, CA
stocker@spacecomputer.com
310 481-6000

Abstract—The most effective hyperspectral (HS) detection techniques rely on some knowledge of target spectra. However, translating laboratory signatures (reflectivity or emissivity) into accurate estimates of remotely sensed spectra is a daunting task without the use of vicarious calibration sources artificially implanted in a scene. It is, on the other hand, more feasible to predict how a signature *changes* over time, if its source remains situated within a single geographic area that is sensed at two times.

Here we develop a family of transforms, called Covariance Equalization (CE), for estimating signature evolution using only the “before” and “after” statistics of an ensemble of HS measurements. CE derives from a linear model of the temporal development of terrestrial background spectra—of natural chromodynamics. The minimum mean squared error solution to the corresponding estimation problem (matrix Wiener filter) depends on cross-correlations between the measurements, knowledge of which requires pixel-level image registration. CE transforms are designed to approximate this optimal solution, without depending on cross-correlations. The resulting estimators, when applied to a full image, effect color-constancy in the sense of preserving all first- and second-order statistics.

The CE family is useful in many multivariate problems, for matching two point sets without use of point to point correspondences. The details of the application determine which member is most appropriate. Here we describe one choice that has worked well in HS imaging problems, and another for multi-modal or -temporal spatial imaging problems. Preliminary tests of the spectral version on remotely sensed HS data indicate that it performs indistinguishably from the optimal method, while obviating the latter’s stressing registration requirement.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Hyperspectral (HS) imaging algorithms can detect sub-pixel changes in large terrestrial scenes sensed many days apart at much lower false alarm rates than are feasible with one-pass methods. The principal obstacle that these techniques must overcome is distinguishing the multitude of naturally occurring background changes from anomalous ones. They do this by exploiting the approximate conservation of certain optical properties associated with persistent background constituents. For example, the individual abundances of a set of background constituents in any given pixel should remain constant, despite changing environmental influences. The associated effective reflectivity (in the visible and short-wave infrared) or emissivity (in the long-wave infrared) should be conserved, despite large potential changes in measured radiance at any one wavelength. Any large excursion from conservation that is implied by the sensed spectrum of a pixel signifies an intrinsic change in the pixel’s physical composition.

The most effective documented algorithm for hyperspectral change detection, called Chronochrome [1], employs a linearized version of this chromodynamics model to construct a matrix Wiener filter. The method therefore requires multi-temporal correlation statistics. Collecting these requires pixel-level registration, which is difficult in most remote sensing applications. But when registration is feasible, a linear mapping statistically connecting HS

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imaging spectra at multiple times can be derived. It effectuates an approximate "color constancy" across times, enabling the meaningful comparison of temporally separated spectral intensity signals.

This mapping defines a spectral evolution operator, which can be exploited for a related purpose: the translating of target signatures from one set of environmental conditions to another. By requiring only first- and second-order hyperspectral statistics to construct a linear transformation, Chronochrome defines a robust method of modeling atmospheric and other environmental effects that modify the apparent signature of every pixel. It therefore expands the potential province of hyperspectral-based target detection, albeit with a restrictive registration requirement.

This paper reviews the principles of the Chronochrome technique for change detection and target signature evolution. It then derives a new technique called Covariance Equalization (CE) that does not require image registration. CE thus removes one of the most difficult engineering impediments to the full exploitation of multi-temporal hyperspectral imagery.

Covariance Equalization embodies a new, generally applicable multiple regression technique, useful in the absence of point-to-point association knowledge between two multivariate data sets. CE can also be interpreted as a new, data-dependent method of decomposing an arbitrary linear transformation into scaling and rotational components.

2. MOTIVATION

Detection of military and intelligence targets by airborne autonomous electro-optical reconnaissance systems is an important evolving capability associated with the maturation of HS camera technology. In recent years it has become clear that the primary factor limiting the effectiveness of these systems is no longer hardware performance, but the difficulties in predicting *in situ* spectra of the targets of interest. A similar problem exists in commercial applications. Laboratory reflectance spectra of materials sought by remote sensing systems must be translated into the spectral intensities measured in the field with an imaging spectrometer. And this must be accomplished without the use of vicarious calibration sources, such as flat panels.

The CE method can be used to define an advanced autonomous HS target detection system [Pat. Pend., Navy Case No. 84,039] that circumvents some of the fundamental problems in the generation of remotely sensed target signatures. It does this by focusing on repeatable missions, with typical revisit intervals of at least several hours, and potentially much longer—perhaps years.

The method assumes that a target has been detected, located, and validated on the first mission, perhaps at a false alarm rate too great to permit stand-alone operation in a wide-area surveillance application. The detection/validation operation could be achieved by standard spectral anomaly detectors used to cue a higher-level decision-maker, or by ground intelligence. Once the target's location is known, its spectral signature from the first mission is captured for use on subsequent missions. This allows the more efficient detection of new, similar targets, as well as the tracking of the original target. However, the concept is viable only if the captured signature can be correctly evolved to account for the new background and environmental conditions associated with the later missions.

A method that achieves this can be developed by modifying the derivation of the Chronochrome algorithm.

3. CHRONOCHROME CHANGE DETECTION

Let $\{x\}$ and $\{y\}$ represent two mean-centered sets of remotely sensed HS signals, generated by the same scene at two times. Each N -dimensional measurement is associated with one ground pixel. In order to detect anomalous changes, such as could be caused by the insertion of manmade objects into the scene or by environmental events, one can construct a linear model of the natural spectral changes—the background chromodynamics—using the statistics encoded in the (spectral) covariance matrices

$$X \equiv \langle xx^t \rangle, \quad Y \equiv \langle yy^t \rangle, \quad (1)$$

and the temporal (/spectral) covariance matrix

$$C \equiv \langle yx^t \rangle, \quad (2)$$

where the brackets indicate expected value.

A linear estimate of the y -data from the x -data

$$y \approx Lx \quad (3)$$

generates an associated error matrix

$$E = \langle (y - Lx)(y - Lx)^t \rangle, \quad (4)$$

which can be rewritten:

$$E = \langle \left\{ (y - CX^{-1}x) + (CX^{-1} - L)x \right\} \times \left\{ (y - CX^{-1}x) + (CX^{-1} - L)x \right\} \rangle, \quad (5)$$

in which it has been assumed that the data $\{x\}$ inhabit all available spectral dimensions, so that X is nonsingular.

When the two factors are multiplied, the cross terms vanish identically, resulting in

$$E = \left\langle (y - CX^{-1}x)(y - CX^{-1}x)^t \right\rangle + (CX^{-1} - L)X(CX^{-1} - L)^t. \quad (6)$$

The mean squared error (mse) associated with the estimator L is given by the trace of the error matrix (see (4) and note that $tr(AB) = tr(BA) = BA$ if BA is a scalar), and so Equation (6) implies

$$tr(E) = \left\langle (y - CX^{-1}x)^t (y - CX^{-1}x) \right\rangle + tr \left[(CX^{-1} - L)X(CX^{-1} - L)^t \right]. \quad (7)$$

Because both terms are nonnegative, the first, being independent of L , represents a lower limit on the error, which can be achieved by the minimum mse solution:

$$L_{CC} = CX^{-1}, \quad (8)$$

known spectrally as the chronochrome (CC) transformation, and mathematically as a matrix Wiener filter.

The simplest form of the chronochrome change detection algorithm consists of transforming the data from mission one with L_{cc} and then applying an anomaly detector, such as the RX algorithm [2], to the error signal

$$\varepsilon = (y - CX^{-1}x). \quad (9)$$

Large (as defined by the associated error matrix) excursions from the norm indicate an intrinsic change. However, calculating the error signal presumes the ability to associate each pixel measurement x from mission one with a co-located one y from mission two. This association is also required for the estimation of the temporal covariance C , Equation (2). For HS remote sensing, this means pixel-level registration accuracy.

4. COVARIANCE EQUALIZATION

Covariance Equalization (CE) is an alternative to the Chronochrome transformation (Equation (8)) that imposes no image registration requirements on the sensing system.

To derive it, we expand Equation (4), using Equations (1) and (2):

$$E = Y - LC^t - CL^t + LXL^t. \quad (10)$$

The only factor requiring registration is C , which we can approximate, using Equations (3) and (2). Then Equation (10) becomes:

$$E \approx Y - LXL^t. \quad (11)$$

This implies an approximate mean square error

$$tr(E) \approx tr(Y) - tr(LXL^t) = tr(Y) - tr(XL^tL). \quad (12)$$

However, because X is a nonnegative matrix, the last term can be made arbitrarily negative, simply by scaling L by a large number. The new L would clearly represent an abuse of the approximation for the (nonnegative) mse, $tr(E)$, and so we adopt a “not too greedy” philosophy and satisfy ourselves with requiring that the approximate mse be zero.

This, however, imposes a constraint on only the trace of Equation (11). A convenient *matrix* constraint that incorporates the trace condition is to require the full approximate covariance matrix E in Equation (11) to be zero. Thus, the approximate solution satisfies

$$L_{CE}XL_{CE}^t = Y, \quad (13)$$

which is the defining equation for the *Covariance Equalization* family of transformations. As a sanity check, we note that if Equation (3) holds exactly, then multiplying it by its transpose and averaging shows that the true transform L also satisfies Equation (13).

Because X and Y are symmetric matrices, they can be diagonalized by orthonormal transformations:

$$X = \Lambda_X D_X \Lambda_X^t, \quad Y = \Gamma_Y D_Y \Gamma_Y^t, \quad (14)$$

where Λ_X, Γ_Y are orthonormal matrices, and D_X, D_Y are diagonal. Because X and Y are, furthermore, non-negative, so are the entries of D_X and D_Y , which means that symmetric square root matrices can be defined:

$$X^{1/2} \equiv \Lambda_X D_X^{1/2} \Lambda_X^t, \quad Y^{1/2} \equiv \Gamma_Y D_Y^{1/2} \Gamma_Y^t. \quad (15)$$

Then Equation (13) can be manipulated to

$$\left(Y^{-1/2} L_{CE} X^{1/2} \right) \left(Y^{-1/2} L_{CE} X^{1/2} \right)^t = 1. \quad (16)$$

This is the definition of orthonormality, so that the general solution can be written

$$L_{CE} = Y^{1/2} R X^{-1/2}, \quad (17)$$

with R some orthonormal matrix. The best choice of R depends on the application. For HS imagery, we have found

that the choice $R = I$ (the identity matrix) works well, in that L_{CE} and L_{CC} produce nearly the same results (see §6).

However, CE is a general multivariate technique, and in §5 we describe a more conventional, non-spectral application. In that case a different choice of R is appropriate.

Notice that the prediction \hat{y} of y based on Equation (17)

$$\hat{y} = L_{CE}x \tag{18}$$

is endowed with the same covariance structure as y ,

$$\hat{Y} \equiv \langle \hat{y}\hat{y}' \rangle = Y, \tag{19}$$

whence the name Covariance Equalization.

Data-Dependent Matrix Decomposition

Besides defining CE, Equation (17) suggests a new, *Data-Dependent Decomposition* (D^3) of an arbitrary matrix L ,

$$L = Y^{1/2}RX^{-1/2} \tag{20}$$

valid whenever the domain data set $\{x\}$ of L is varied enough—i.e. occupies all available dimensions, so that its covariance matrix X is invertible. Any linear transformation L can then be decomposed into a 3-step process (see Figure 1), consisting of two scaling and one orthonormal operations: (1) Whitening by $X^{-1/2}$ to produce an uncorrelated data set; (2) Rotation by R (plus a possible axis inversion); and (3) Re-coloring the data to conform to the correlation structure of the range data set $\{y\}$, for which Equation (3) holds exactly. This latter condition insures that R is orthonormal. For, using it and Equation (20),

$$Y \equiv \langle yy' \rangle = \langle (Lx)(Lx)' \rangle = LXL' = Y^{1/2}RR'Y^{1/2}, \tag{21}$$

from which it follows that

$$RR' = 1. \tag{22}$$

Figure 1. Illustration of the three steps in the *Data-Dependent Decomposition* (D^3) of a linear transformation.

Thus, according to Equation (20), knowing how a transform L modifies the data statistics from X to Y allows one to express L in a constrained form. All remaining ignorance of L is concentrated in the rotation (/inversion) R , with $\frac{N}{2}(N-1)$ degrees of freedom, instead of the N^2 associated with an arbitrary linear transform.

Relation to SVD

If the matrix X in Equation (20) is *chosen* to be the identity then, with the help of Equation (15), L simplifies to

$$L = (\Gamma_Y D_Y^{1/2} \Gamma_Y') R. \tag{23}$$

The first term ($= Y^{1/2}$) has as eigenvectors the columns of the matrix Γ_Y , and so represents N simultaneous rescalings in those orthogonal directions. Equation (23) shows that any linear transformation can be thought of as a rotation followed by a scaling. Regrouping it as

$$L = (\Gamma_Y) D_Y^{1/2} (\Gamma_Y' R) \tag{24}$$

reveals its equivalence to the Singular Value Decomposition (SVD) of L , which is a diagonal matrix bracketed by two orthonormal ones. Thus the D^3 includes the SVD as a special case. The orthonormal transform $\Gamma_Y R$ derived from the SVD of any transform $L = \Gamma D \Lambda'$ can be thought of as its rotational part, and $\Gamma D \Gamma'$ as its scaling part

$$L = (\Gamma D \Gamma') (\Gamma \Lambda'). \tag{25}$$

Relation to Multiple Regression

Equation (18) can be interpreted as a type of linear regression of y on x . Similarly, the standard method of multiple regression uses the transform in Equation (8), which minimizes the y -error, given by the trace of Equation (4). In the special case where the x and y variables are both one-dimensional, Equation (8) defines the slope of the regression line. Conversely, the regression of x on y results in a different regression line, one that minimizes the x -error. The corresponding slope is $C^{-1}Y$.

The geometric mean of the slopes of these two standard regression lines is thus $\sqrt{CX^{-1}C^{-1}Y} = Y^{1/2}X^{-1/2}$, which equals the slope of the regression line generated by CE, Equation (17). (Note that, being a 1×1 orthonormal matrix, R must now be either 1 or -1. And variance information alone cannot reveal the sign of the correlation.)

Thus Covariance Equalization can be thought of as a regression technique intermediate to the two minimum mse techniques.

5. CHOOSING THE ROTATION

The ambiguity associated in the one-dimensional case with the sign of the correlation is much greater in higher dimensions. The orthonormal R then becomes a possible inversion *and* an unknown rotation.

However, without the correlation information contained in the matrix C , a purely mathematical analysis can take us no further in determining the appropriate choice of R in Equation (17). This is, instead, dictated by the particulars of the problem.

3-D Imaging

If the beginning- and end-shapes in Figure 1 represent rigid bodies in physical (i.e., not spectral) three-dimensional space, then L could represent a change in viewing aspect and magnification. Several examples arise in medical imaging, such as co-registering: (1) multi-modal images (MRI and PET scans [3]); or (2) multi-temporal single modes (Wang applies related ideas to two mammograms taken three years apart [3]).

In these cases, the covariance matrices are analogous to moment of inertia matrices and the eigenvectors to the principal axes of a solid object. If viewing angles can change, then a rotational component in L (Equation (20)) is clearly in order, and the D^3 illustrated in Figure 1 suggests that the natural choice is

$$R = \Gamma_Y \Lambda'_X. \quad (26)$$

This rotates the principal axes of X into those of Y . The association ambiguity generated by the lack of registration information is present here, but in a mild form. The rotation in Equation (26) depends on how the columns of Γ_Y are permuted relative to those of Λ_X . An obvious choice is to arrange the columns of both Λ_X and Γ_Y in (say) decreasing order of the corresponding eigenvalues D_X and D_Y . There is also a relative sign ambiguity in the same columns that can be resolved by requiring that the diagonal entries of $\Lambda'_X \Gamma_Y$ be nonnegative, corresponding to (assumed) small rotations.

To summarize, a natural choice from the CE family (Equation (17)) for (spatial) imaging applications is

$$L_I = Y^{1/2} \Gamma_Y \Lambda'_X X^{-1/2}. \quad (27)$$

Using Equation (15), this simplifies to

$$L_I = \Gamma_Y D_Y^{-1/2} D_X^{1/2} \Lambda'_X, \quad (28)$$

which has the same content as Equation (10) of [3]. (We remark that the inverse diagonal term in Equation (28) renders the transformation L_I sensitive to noise. A better choice [5], assuming that the $\{y\}$ and $\{x\}$ data are related by a magnification (M), a rotation (R), and additive noise, is

$$L_{MR} = \left(\frac{tr(Y)}{tr(X)} \right)^{1/2} \Gamma_Y \Lambda'_X. \quad (29)$$

This is, however, *not* a member of the CE family. Like CE, however, it solves an approximate optimization problem, but for a specific (MR) physical model. It equalizes only the traces of the covariance matrices.)

Hyperspectral Imaging

Absent any detailed phenomenological model to describe the HS content of terrestrial backgrounds, one must choose R in Equation (17) using general principles.

To this end, we discuss two of the more important classes of mechanisms that account for statistical differences in HS images collected at two different times.

First, changes in apparent path radiance from the ground to the sensor. These arise from variations in haze levels, as well as from offset drift in sensor readouts. Both these effect changes in first-order statistics, which are automatically accounted for in the above analysis by its reliance on mean-centered variables at both times.

Second, changes in illumination level (or temperature and down-welling radiation in emissive wavelength regions); in attenuation from time-varying concentrations of atmospheric aerosols and gases; and in sensor electronic gain levels. These effects all change the measured variances in all spectral channels. Furthermore, each of these effects tends to induce correlated changes across wavelength. For example, natural illumination levels will tend to grow (or shrink) at *all* wavelengths; increased aerosol levels will tend to attenuate *all* spectral signals, as well as *all* their variabilities.

If there were physical changes in the environment tending to increase variability in some wavelengths, but decrease it in others, one could expect a "torqueing" effect on the corresponding spectral scatterplot, as in Figure 1. This would imply the need for the rotational component allowed in Equation (17). The absence of any relevant phenomenology to generate this effect supports a rotation-free choice of CE for HS applications:

$$L_{HS} = Y^{1/2} X^{-1/2}. \quad (30)$$

One important advantage of this choice for L —i.e. with $R=I$ —is its invariance to any permutation or sign changes in the columns of either Λ_X or Γ_Y (see Equation (15)). This makes it unambiguously defined, unlike for example, the rotation of Equation (26).

Another advantage is its performance.

6. TESTS OF HS COVARIANCE EQUALIZATION

The relative ability of the HS version of CE (Equation (30)) vs. the minimum error solution CC (Equation (8)) to predict signature evolution can be assessed using pairs of well-registered HS images. Such data sets permit the estimation of the temporal correlation matrix C , which is required for CC.

Because CE is designed to substitute for CC, a stringent test of its efficacy can be made by using it to challenge Chronochrome in its native application, change detection. As a reference, Figure 2 shows HS static (one-pass) detection performance for the most common form of anomaly detector, the RX algorithm, applied in a stressing (cluttered) background environment (Airborne data taken at 0.4-1.0 μm wavelengths from NRL's WARHORSE program [4]). In its simplest form, RX is a threshold comparison test of the statistic

$$x'X^{-1}x. \tag{31}$$

Varying the threshold generates the curves of Figure 2.

Figure 2. Performance results, visible/near infrared data. The two lower curves show the results of searching for spectral anomalies in a stressing background. The change detector Chronochrome decreases false alarms by a factor of 100, but Covariance Equalization, with no registration requirement, works about as well.

RX is also used in the final stage of the two change detection algorithms characterized in Figure 2. One of these is standard chronochrome using the predictor L from

Equation (8); the other uses the CE form Equation (30). For change detection, RX is applied to the prediction error, not the mean-centered radiance. That is,

$$(y - Lx)' \left\{ (y - Lx)(y - Lx)' \right\}^{-1} (y - Lx) \tag{32}$$

(cf. Equation (31)) is compared to a threshold. The figure shows that the performance of CC- and CE-based methods are nearly identical (within the statistical error). Both enhance performance over standard anomaly detection by two orders of magnitude in false alarm rate reduction.

In a second test of CE performance, its ability to predict signature evolution directly was compared to that of CC. Figure 3 shows the apparent emissivity in the long-wave infrared (8-12 μm) of ground targets sensed with the SEBASS imaging spectrometer, on two different days. In each case, airborne data-derived estimates of the ground temperature were combined with the Planck function to estimate emissivity from sensed radiance. The CE-based method of evolving the radiance signature produces nearly

Figure 3. LWIR signatures derived from airborne HS sensor. Top and bottom curves shown apparent signatures from measurements made one day apart. Predictions of Day 2 signatures based on Chronochrome (CC) or Covariance Equalization (CE) are nearly identical.

the same emissivity prediction as CC, which is derived from a minimum error fit of the HS background data on the two days. And, both predictions are reasonably close to the measured Day 2 signature.

These preliminary investigations indicate that the Covariance Equalizing transform in Equation (30) can replace the minimum mse Chronochrome estimate (Equation (8)) with little effect on performance, in either HS change detection or signature prediction applications. Achieving Wiener filter-like performance appears to be possible without knowledge of cross-temporal covariance structures requiring pixel-level registration accuracy.

7. SUMMARY

An equation ((13)) has been derived that defines a family (CE) of linear transformations connecting one multivariate data set to another. The transformation achieves perfect equalization of all first- and second-order statistical moments. The solution to the equation was derived in its full generality (Equation (17)), and it was found to admit an arbitrary N-dimensional rotation/inversion.

A particular CE member (Equation (27)) was proposed for 3-D imaging applications. It suggested, when integrated with a simple model of image differences, an improved estimator (Equation (29)) of image changes.

A particular CE member (Equation (30)) was suggested for hyperspectral applications. It was tested on data that had been accurately registered, and this permitted a comparison with the optimal methods, which require registration. Initial tests of change detection and signature evolution have shown that the hyperspectral version of Covariance Equalization generates comparable performance to those using the optimal method.

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Biographies

Dr. Alan Schaum received a Ph.D. in Theoretical Physics in 1978 from The Johns Hopkins University, where his research focused on relativistic quantum field theory. Until 1983 he worked at Bell Laboratories in Holmdel New Jersey, applying queuing and information theories to network planning problems. For the past 19 years at the Naval Research Laboratory in Washington D.C., he has developed signal and image processing methods in support of intelligence operations. He is the first author of 60 technical publications and co-author of another 20. His current research emphasizes hyperspectral detection theory

and the modeling of terrestrial background signatures and their dynamics.

Alan Stocker (picture not available) has been Vice President of Space Computer Corporation, Los Angeles, since 1987. He received his MSEE from Stanford University in 1981 and previously worked at Hughes Aircraft Company and MARK Resources, Inc. For the past 10 years his primary technical focus has been the design, development and implementation of data processing algorithms for multispectral and hyperspectral imaging sensors. He has authored over 30 papers on various aspects of hyperspectral data analysis and processing, including sensor correction and calibration, automatic target detection and recognition, and real-time systems.